

EMPLOYEE **ONBOARDING AND INDUSTRIAL HARMONY** OF SELECTED BAKERY'S IN PORT HARCOURT, RIVERS STATE

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Abstract: *The study investigated the relationship between employee onboarding and industrial harmony in some selected bakery's in Port Harcourt, Nigeria, the research addressed a critical gap by examining onboarding not merely as an administrative function but as a strategic intervention of fostering long- team woke place peace. The study was anchored on organizational socialization theory, which posits that structured early experience are crucial for integrating new comers into an organization social and cultural fabric. A cross sectional survey research designs was employed, and data was collected from a sample of 399 workers selected from a population using the taro yamen formula. A structured questionnaire was used to gather data on the dimension of employee on boarding (orientation and training) the measure of industries harmony (employer-employee cooperation). Data analysis involved descriptive statistics and spearman's rank order correlation, performed with SPSS version 26.0 to test the hypothesis at a 0.01 significance level. The key finding revealed statistically significant positive relationship between the onboarding dimension and industrial harmony measures. The study concluded that a well structured on boarding process, which effectively incorporates clear orientation, fosters social integration and provides job clarity, is a fundamental determinant of industrial harmony. It serves to build trust, facilitate open communication and align employee expectation with organizational goals from the outset, thereby promoting a cooperate work environment.*

Keywords: *Onboarding, industrial harmony, orientation, training, employer, employee.*

INTRODUCTION

Industrial harmony remains a critical determinant of organizational stability and operational continuity. In the case of bakery's in Port Harcourt, industrial harmony signifies the state of peaceful and co-operative relation among employees, the trade union within the organization. This peace is characterized by the absence of industrial unrest, strikes, disputes, or disruptive labor, conflicts action that can impair productivity and erode corporate reputation. These conflicts underscore a growing concern: how well organizational practices align with workers' expectation and social contract. According to

Longe (2024), industrial harmony is an organized workplace, where labour and management as prime movers of the operational activities collaborate willingly in pursuit of corporate goals' accomplishment. The underlining assumption here, is that, industrial harmony is the soul of an organization and an uncommon fruit of a mature system of industrial relations which is pivotal to stable and productive work relations.

When this balance is disrupted, the result is often poor morale, loss of man-hours, high turnovers rate and grievances. According to Atairet and Emmanuel (2022), there is hardly any organisation that can function smoothly at all times without grievance. Naturally, where two or a group of persons agree to come together to do a particular task, grievances may naturally set in. It is therefore, necessary for a proper mechanism on how grievances could be redressed or resolved, to be spelt out clearly, to pave way for how to co-exist harmoniously.

In this light, a growing body of practical concern focusing on employee onboarding as a foundational activity that could significantly shape trajectory of industrial harmony in firms such as Bakery. Employee onboarding refers to a structured process of introducing new employees to the organizational culture, systems, expectation and performance requirement. It goes beyond the basic orientation process to include job clarity, mentorship and early in team dynamics. According to Sofia, Patricia and Carlos (2024), when there is not an adequate onboarding process for new employees, it causes problems adapting to an organizational culture, low employee productivity, lack of knowledge of rules, policies, and lack of communication. Because of this, in organizations, new employees are very vulnerable when they begin to generate the corresponding activities, since their training and induction was not in an efficient and timely manner to acquire the knowledge of said position and this will generate various errors in the internal processes of the organization (Sofia, Patricia & Carlos, 2024). In contrast, a robust onboarding program can help new hires feels valued, informed, and integrated, thereby building a sense of belonging and mutual respect the reinforces peaceful labor- management relations

According to Umar, Rosmelisa and Hazril (2022) effective onboarding aims to help new hires feel more at ease in their new roles, effective onboarding can facilitate increased employee commitment to the organization by increasing job satisfaction. Onboarding enhances employee trust in management, which is a central pillar of industrial harmony. Trust is fostered when new hires perceive transparency, fairness, and open line of communication from their first day. This initial impression shapes their long-term engagement, loyalty, and attitudes toward the employer. When onboarding is neglected or poorly executed, it can generate skepticism and a perception of neglect, particularly in firms with prior histories of labor unrest. In such environment, even minor grievances can snowball into industrial action due to the absence of foundational trust built during the onboarding phase.

Hence, the link between employee onboarding and industrial harmony in Bakery, Port Harcourt, is both direct and consequential. Industrial peace does not occur spontaneously; it is cultivated through deliberate, inclusive, and consistent practices that begin at the point of the entry into the organization. Onboarding serve as the foundation for establishing norms, building relationship and clarifying roles and expectations. If properly harnessed, it can significantly reduce misunderstandings, foster early alignment, and promote a positive work culture that resist divisive tendencies. In contrast, neglecting this crucial phase can lead to entrenchment of distrust, the perpetuation of grievances and eventual breakdowns in labor relations.

Although several studies have examined the dynamics of industrial harmony and the factors that contribute to its sustenance, limited empirical attention has been paid to the role of the employee onboarding, particularly within high-risk and labor-sensitive sectors such as oil and gas industry. For instance, Nwosu (2018) did a study on collective bargaining; a panacea for industrial harmony and efficient service delivery in the workplace, concluded that once an organization is set up, there is bound to be conflict and when this arises, collective bargaining is one of the major methods in settling it, which is generally a road map in ensuring industrial harmony and efficient service delivery in the workplace. Edet, Uduak & Eno (2024) did a study on The Impact of Trade Unionism on Staff Welfare in Nigerian Public Institutions which underscores the importance of understanding the dynamics between staff advocacy mechanisms and welfare outcomes. Their study further explained that while lobbying and strikes can bring attention to staff issues and potentially lead to improvements, they also require careful management to avoid negative consequences.

While these studies provided valuable insights into traditional element of labor relations, they largely overlooked onboarding as a preemptive and strategic human resources tool that shape employee perception, expectations, and organizational alignment from the outset.

More so, the few available studies that address onboarding often treat it as a performance-related variable linked to employee productivity, retention or engagement but rarely connect it to broader organizational outcomes such as industrial harmony. This narrow lens fails to capture the strategic value of onboarding in fostering long-term labor peace and collaborate work environment. In the specific context of Niger delta, where employment practices are politically and socially charged, onboarding could play a transformative role in shaping employee attitude and minimizing friction. Yet, existing literature has not sufficiently explored this link.

This gap is particularly glaring in studies related to bakery's in Port Harcourt, where onboarding policies are often generalized or underreported in organizational assessments. There is a lack of context specific research that situates onboarding within the framework of industrial harmony in a volatile, oil-producing region. Therefore, this study departs

from conventional labor relations research by interrogating how early-stage human resource practices specifically onboarding can be used as a strategic intervention for promoting industrial harmony in bakery. Thus, it seek to reimagining onboarding not as a routine administration task, but as a foundational determinant of labor peace and organizational cohesion in conflict-prone environments.

Despite management's acknowledgement of the importance of onboarding, recurring incidents of labor unrest, passive resistance, and employment dissatisfaction suggest that the onboarding framework remains underutilized as a tool for promoting industrial harmony. What lags behind is holistic, strategic approach that not only introduces new employees to their tasks but also prepares them for collaborative coexistence with management and peers. Furthermore, previous studies have largely focused on external industrial peace, with limited scholarly exploration into how internal human resources practices like onboarding can preempt conflict from the point entry. This study departs from such traditional perspectives by examining employee onboarding not just as an administrative procedure but as a strategic driver of industrial harmony. The present investigation seeks to fill this gap by exploring how onboarding practices in Bakery influence employee, trust-building, and ultimately, labor peace.

Add problem of the study

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK **Is employer-employee an outcome?**

Fig. 1.1: Conceptual framework showing the relationship between employee onboarding and industrial harmony in Bakery.

Sources: Bauer, T. N. (2013); Obibhunun (2021); Research (2025).

Add your research questions

HYPOTHESIS

The hypothesis was stated in null form;

H₀₁: Orientation has no significant relationship with employer-employee cooperation of Bakery's in Port Harcourt.

H₀₂: Training has no significant relationship with employer-employee cooperation of Bakery's in Port Harcourt.

Conceptual framework b4 theoretical

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The underpinning theory of this study is the organizational socialization theory. This was originally developed by John Van Maanen and Edgar H. Schein in 1979. The theory centers on the process through which newcomers acquire the necessary knowledge, skills, attitudes and behaviors to become effective members of an organization. Van Maanen and Schein posit that organizational socialization is a critical mechanism through which individuals transition from being outsiders to becoming integrated insiders who understand the cultural procedural and interpersonal dynamics of their new work environment. The theory opines that socialization is not merely about introducing job task, but about embedding new employees into the social and cultural fabric of the organization. It emphasizes structured interactions, role clarity, performance expectation, mentoring and early-stage feedback as essential tools to help newcomers internalize workplace norms and values. The central idea is that the more systematic and supportive the onboarding experience is, the more likely the employee is to adjust effectively, align with organization goals and maintain a stable relationship with colleagues and supervisors.

CONCEPTUAL REVIEW remove

CONCEPT OF EMPLOYEE ONBOARDING

According to Logesh & Priyadharshini (2024) onboarding is the process of helping the company's new hires and making them adjust to the social and performance aspects of their jobs as quickly as possible. Employee on boarding refers to the structured process through which new employees are integrated into an organization, equipped with the knowledge, skills, and behaviours required to become effective organizational members. Within the complex operational environment of Bakery, on boarding plays a particular strategic role due to the technical nature of the bakery, the safety-sensitive work setting, and the diverse workforce composed of both expatriate and indigenous employees. In many multinational co-operation, on boarding is essential for aligning employees with global standards while also contextualizing their roles within local realities. As noted by Bhagyashree, Poonam & Vandana (2025) onboarding can be characterized as a integration program that provides new employees with the necessary resources to become fully engaged and culturally aware members of a productive workforce. Further it can also be defined as assimilation, organizational entrance, or employee socialization a process wherein a new employee is acquainted with the goal, vision, and values of a company (Bhagyashree, et al. 2025).

DIMENSIONS OF EMPLOYEE ON BOARDING

Orientation

Orientation is a fundamental dimension of employee on boarding, serving as the initial structured intervention through which new hires are introduced to an organizations culture, policies, expectations, and work environment. In the context of Bakery, a national bakery with variety and array's of products with complex operational demands, orientation plays a critical role in setting the tone for employee engagement, safety compliance, and industrial alignment.

According to Bauer (2013) orientation help new employees understand many important aspects of their jobs and organizations, including the company's culture and values, its goals and history, and its power structure. Orientation programs also serve a social role, helping newcomers feel welcome by introducing them to their co-workers and other individuals within the organization. Orientations, which may last a few hours to a few months, can provide new employees with valuable information and the chance to process a lot of paperwork and procedures quickly, using tools that include discussions, lectures, videotapes and written material (Bauer, 2013).

For Bakery, this process also includes comprehensive safety training sessions, given the hazardous chemical nature of production. New employees are expected to understand the intricacies of safety protocols, emergency response procedures, and environmental sustainability policies.

Training

A new employee needs the confidence, clarity and skills to do the job he or she has been hired to do. According to Bauer (2013) potential training for new employees includes hard skills, soft skills and onboarding skills, and each skill set is important. If a new employee has low levels of self-efficacy at the start, training is even more necessary to boost subsequent ability to cope and job performance. Training can show newcomers how to proactively help their own adjustment and therefore encourage successful onboarding (Bauer, 2013).

Timothy, Abu, Idonije & Isah (2020) explained that Employee training is a planned activity which focuses on increasing and enlarging the capabilities, improving the technical and conceptual skills of employees so that they can posses the necessary abilities to handle complex situations and better perform their job. The central idea underlying training in any sector is how best to keep employees current, vibrant and versatile so that they can continuously perform their roles effectively in this age of rapid socio-economic, political, scientific and technological changes and globalization.

Through the help training, new employees will be socially well-integrated and become more likely to exhibit organizational commitment, communicate openly with colleagues, and comply with safety and performance standards of the organization.

CONCEPT OF INDUSTRIAL HARMONY

Industrial harmony refers to a state of peaceful coexistence, mutual respect, and effective collaboration between employees and management within an organization. In the context of Bakery, maintaining such a stable work environment is not just a human resource ideal but a strategic imperative. The company's operations are labor-intensive, technologically complex and often exposed to external socio-political pressures, making harmonious industrial relations a cornerstone of sustainable productivity and organizational continuity.

Industrial harmony is the relationship between management and workers about terms and conditions of employment and the workplace (Tamunobere and Tamunoniebi, 2023). In actuality, it is a scenario where management and staff freely collaborate to accomplish the objectives of the company (Jakpa & Ibegbulem, 2025).

According to Akuh (2016), industrial harmony enhances labour productivity and in turn improves performance in our education sector, achieving economic growth, and enhancing living standards and quality of life. It creates a peaceful working environment conducive to tolerance, dialogue and other alternative (to strike) means of resolving industrial or labour disputes in Nigeria (such as negotiation, mediation, arbitration, conciliation and litigation or court adjudication). This creates a high level of employee satisfaction.

MEASURES OF INDUSTRIAL HARMONY

Employer-Employee Cooperation

An employer is an individual or organization that recruits people to work on their behalf. It can direct the work of its employees, including dictating where, when, and how work is completed (Obibhunun, 2021). More specifically, an employer is an organization, institution, government entity, agency, company, professional services firm, nonprofit association, small business, store, or individual who employs or puts to work individuals.

An employee is an individual who is employed by another person and is being paid certain amount performance related problems that may arise (Obibhunun, 2021). Other problems like applicable regulations, legislations, negotiations, grievance and appeal rights, bigotry, and whistleblower protections. It involves striking a balance of interests, and it is dedicated to establishing and maintaining a conducive work place to iron out job-related issues.

According to Venkadesa & Saranraj (2017) Employer/employee relations refer to the communication that takes place between representatives of employees and employers.

Much of the employee relations involve employees and employers working together. When an employer hires a new employee, he is not just bringing a new member of the workforce aboard; he is also starting a new relationship. Because employers and employees often work in close quarters, they necessarily develop relationships. Managing these relationships is vital to business success, as strong relationships can lead to greater employee happiness and even increased productivity (Venkadesa & Saranraj, 2017).

Adeyeye (2021) explained that the employer-employee relations are no doubt an enamors aspect in human resources management that covers key functions areas like employment relations, collective bargaining, performance and reward management as well as employee involvement which help to determining the nature of organizational commitment and performance.

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EMPLOYEE ONBOARDING AND INDUSTRIAL HARMONY

Employee on boarding plays a foundational role in shaping early workplace experience, setting the tone for long-term relationship between new hires and the organization. In an industrial environment such as Bakery, where consultation, team cohesion, and compliance with safety and ethical standard are paramount, a structured onboarding process becomes essential for promoting organizational alignment and maintains workplace tranquility. Effective onboarding help in acclimating employees to co-operate expectations, behavioral norms and functional responsibilities, thereby reducing early misunderstanding and potential conflict triggers. According to Bhagyashree et al (2025) well-executed onboarding process include improved productivity, enhanced job satisfaction, and long-term retention.

Industrial harmony refers to a stable and peaceful work environment where mutual interest of management and employees are balanced through collaboration, fairness, and shared purpose. The onboarding phase serve as the employee's initial encounter with the company's culture, policies, and leadership approach. If executed with clarity, mutual respect and consistency, onboarding not only help individuals assimilate efficiency but also lays the groundwork for mutual respect, trust and organizational commitment. As noted by Bhagyashree et al (2025), the onboarding process, perceived as an ongoing journey instead of a singular event, requires a long-term strategy to assist new employees. Participants indicated that specific job elements necessitate continuous direction and assistance, asking for enhanced physical interaction to promote informal discussions vital for socialization. In the bakery industries, where technical skills, safety adherence, and team co-ordination are critical, on boarding becomes more than a formality it is a strategic necessity. New employees often step into high risk roles where errors can have significant consequences. A well designed on boarding programs ensures that individuals are not only technically prepared but also culturally aligned and psychologically engaged. According to Bauer (2013) the ultimate failure of onboarding is the withdrawal of potentially good employees. Losing an employee who is a poor fit or not performing well may be a fine outcome, but losing employees because they are confused, feel alienated or lack confidence indicates inadequate onboarding. Simply put, good onboarding leads to good retention rates. Inadequate on boarding is a common source of early stage

disengagement, communication breakdowns, and procedural non-compliance, which can destabilize team relation and disrupt work flow harmony.

The relationship between on boarding experience shapes perceptions of the organization. If new employees feel welcomed, supported and valued, they are more likely to develop positive attitudes toward the workplace, reducing the likelihood of resistance, dissatisfaction, or disconnection. Bhagyashree et al (2025) explained that a poor first-day experience can have lasting consequences. If employees do not feel valued, welcomed, or adequately guided during this phase, their engagement and connection to the organization suffer. This often leads to a higher likelihood of them leaving the company within a few months to a year. Employees who feel unsupported on day-one may struggle with confidence, clarity about their roles, or alignment with organizational culture, making it harder for them to integrate into the team effectively. Addressing this issue requires a well-structured and thoughtful approach to day-one activities. This includes warm welcomes, clear communication of expectations, a thorough induction, and personalized attention to make employees feel comfortable and motivated (Bhagyashree et al, 2025). That early clarity about roles, communication structures, and behavioral expectations reduces ambiguity and minimizes misinterpretations, both of which are essential for sustaining organizational cohesion and minimizing workplace tension. Bakery, given its complex operational structure and diverse work force, places importance on onboarding as a tool for strengthening internal communication and aligning employee expectations. Through structured programs that include orientation sessions, mentorship initiatives, and role specific training, JEK ensures that new hires are equipped to integrate seamlessly into the workplace. These programs are designed not only to convey technical knowledge but also to instill a sense of belonging and respect for organizational values.

Furthermore, on boarding programs that emphasize two-way communication allow new staff to express concerns, seek clarification, and offer feedback this openness creates a feedback-rich environment where truth is cultivated, and potential issues are addressed before escalating conflict. As observed by Umar et al (2022) that poor and improper information dissemination can bring about confusion, anxiety, and the inability of the newcomer to adjust quickly. Hence it is advised that all efforts to provide information, materials, and experiences should begin with recruitment to help newcomers learn what they need to know to be successful in their new role. And this can be achieved through three subcategories such as; communication, resource and training. Communication includes one-way messages to new employees, e.g., welcome letters, and two-way dialogue, e.g., schedule calls. Resources consist of a new employee Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ) on the company's website, then the training subcategory, which includes programs that empower the newcomer on skills, e.g., orientation program (Umar et al., 2022).

Another dimension of the onboarding industrial harmony relationship lies in way onboarding cultural integration. In a multinational operational context, cultural diversity can be both a strength and challenge. Onboarding processes that incorporate diversity training and inclusion practices help new hires appreciate differences while embracing

shaped goals. Bhagyashree et al (2025) stated that onboarding can be framed through the four C's: Compliance, Clarity, Culture, and Connection. They also stated that for onboarding to be effective requires key levers such as self-efficacy, role clarity, social integration and cultural knowledge that should be tailored to individual needs depending on the employee's background. When individuals understand and respect cultural norms within their work environment from the onset; they are better positioned to interact cooperatively, reducing the likelihood of interpersonal conflict. Beyond individual adjustment, effective on boarding contributes to team cohesion. When new employees are integrated in a consistent and inclusive manner, team dynamics improve, and collaboration becomes more seamless. This coherence fosters a sense of unity and shared responsibility that supports an environment free from disruption.

METHODOLOGY

This study examined the relationship between employee onboarding and industrial harmony of selected Bakery's in Port Harcourt. The study adopted a correlation research design and the primary data was generated through self-administered questionnaire. Information from the Master Baker Association state a total number of 250 bakeries are operating in Rivers state out from which 10 were selected using the simple random sampling technique. (A simple randomization can not product 10 out of 250 firms and you can not generalize with it) The names of the 10 selected bakeries are; Bonjour meals, Goodness bakeries, High taste food, High5 bakery, Tasty bakery, De-Altimate Precious food, JEK catering, Nibbles bakery, Baker Hughes and Delta bakeries. The population of the study consist a totally of 500 staffs from the selected Bakery's in Port Harcourt. The sample size of 399 was determined using the Taro Yamane's formula for sample size determination. The hypotheses were tested using the Pearson Product moment of Correlation with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26.0. The tests were carried out at a 99% confidence interval and a 0.01 level of significance.

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULT

The level of significance 0.01 was adopted as a criterion for the probability of accepting the null hypothesis in ($p > 0.01$) or rejecting the null hypothesis in ($p < 0.01$).

Hypotheses One (H₀₁)

Table 1: Correlations

		ORIENTATION	EMPLOYER_EMPLOYEE
Spearman's rho	ORIENTATION	Correlation Coefficient	.882**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
		N	82
	EMPLOYER_EMPLOYEE	Correlation Coefficient	.882**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
		N	82

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Research Data, 2025

DISCUSSIONS OF FINDINGS

The H₀₁ state that orientation has no significant relationship with consultation. Based on the results of data derived from table 1 above (shows that $r=0.882$, $p=0.000 < 0.01$), the null hypotheses is rejected. This clearly shows that there is a positive significant relationship between orientation and employer-employee cooperation ($r=.882$) which shows a strong correlation.

Hypotheses Two (H₀₂)

Table 2: Correlations

			TRAINING	EMPLOYER_EMPLOYEE
Spearman's rho	TRAINING	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.970**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	82	82
	EMPLOYER_EMPLOYEE	Correlation Coefficient	.970**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	82	82

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Research Data, 2019

DISCUSSIONS OF FINDINGS

The H₀₂ state training has no significant relationship with employer-employee cooperation. In view of the result data stated in table 2 above (shows that $r=0.970$, $p=0.000 < 0.01$), the null hypotheses is rejected. This clearly shows there is a positive significant relationship between training and employer-employee cooperation ($r=.970$) which shows a strong correlation.

SUMMARY

The study was carried out to established the relationship between employees onboarding and industrial harmony of Bakery's in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. The study adopted cross-sectional survey research design to elicit information from the respondent in the Bakery in Port Harcourt; a simple size of three hundred and ninety-nine copies questionnaire or sent out to the respondents in 10 selected Bakery in Port Harcourt. Data collected for the study was through the use of questionnaire and fully analyzed. The Spearman's rank order correlation statistics with the aid of statistical package or social science (SPSS version 26.0) was used to test the null hypotheses at (0.01) level of significant to know the strength and effect of employee on boarding and industrial harmony of selected Bakery's in Port Harcourt. The study found out that there is a significant positive relationship between employee on boarding and industrial harmony of Bakery's in Port Harcourt. Specifically:

1. The finding of the study showed that there is a significant positive relationship between orientation and employer-employee cooperation.
2. The findings of the study showed that there is a significant positive relationship between training and employer-employee cooperation.

CONCLUSION

Base on the finding of this study, it can be concluded that employee on boarding significantly contribute to industrial harmony within Bakery's in Port Harcourt. Specifically, the orientation aspect of onboarding fosters effective employer-employee cooperation. Furthermore, good training enhances employee knowledge to perform efficiently and effectively in their day-to-day work; and ensures mutual respect among employers and employees, which is vital for maintaining a cooperative work environment. Overall, this result underscores the strategic importance of a structured onboarding process as a catalyst for promoting a harmonious industrial atmosphere.

RECOMMENDATIONS in a single sentence form and not paragraph and it should not be more that your objectives

The following recommendations are proposed to enhance employee onboarding and promote industrial harmony at Bakery:

1. The company should institutionalize a structured orientation program that goes beyond basic induction. This program should clearly communicate the company vision, values, policies, and expectation to new employees, while also in cooperating mechanisms for regular consultation and feedback. Doing so will not only align employees with organizational goals but also encourage open communication and participatory decision making.
2. Management should actively promote social integration through team building activities, mentorship schemes, and informal engagement –platforms. These initiatives help new employees build inter personal relationship and foster sense of belonging, which in turn strengthens the effectiveness grievances redressed systems by making employees feel secure and heard.
3. Management should be clearly defined and communicated at the point of on boarding. This includes setting expectations, performance standards, and reporting lines: clarity in job functions enhances accountability, reduces workplace conflict, and builds mutual respect among colleagues and supervisors.

4. The human resources department should routinely evaluate and refine on boarding processes based on employee feedback and evolving organizational need. Continues improvement will ensure the on boarding strategy remain effective in sustaining a harmonious and productive work environment.

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